

Lived Experiences of Adversity in Emerging Adulthood: A Qualitative Study in Indian Context

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Emerging adulthood is a significant developmental stage (18-29 years) of transformation from adolescence to adulthood. It is a phase of life where adults explore major life choices, career transitions, relationships and future life possibilities. It is a period marked by changes, uncertainties and adversities throughout their adulthood. While emerging adulthood is prevalent in affluent Western societies, the form of manifestation and its relevance in the Indian context remain underexplored. This research is rooted in qualitative methodology and explores how emerging adults (18-29 years) in India experience and navigate adversities, and how these experiences shape them. Through semi-structured interviews with individuals who have faced distressing or traumatic events, key themes are identified and analysed using Reflexive Thematic Analysis. Some of the themes being: Negotiating roles and responsibilities, identity formation and self-development, emotional struggles and psychological impact, coping mechanisms and resilience, societal pressures and restraints, and future orientation. The study provides important insights into what characterises emerging adulthood in the Indian cultural contexts in normal or adverse situations and has implications for understanding how young adults negotiate transitions within complex socio-cultural environments.

Keywords: Emerging adulthood, adversities, Indian culture, reflexive thematic analysis, qualitative research

Adulthood, a period where one wishes to find stability and balance within oneself, this transitioning phase of life that moulds an individual into what they desire to become. This stage of life defines an individual's personality, relationships and career. This understanding reshapes, fragments and develops itself along with time. Adults in the modern-day world juggle between managing their own aspirations and fulfilling the societal expectations of achieving stability. Every adult views the definition of being stable very differently from each other; they try to pave their own paths. While defining these paths, every single one of them faces opportunities as well as inequalities, playing an important role in how young people transition into adult life; the time of emerging adulthood is not only a time of freedom and exploration but also the time to face real-world obstacles (Cote & Bynner, 2008).

Emerging Adulthood, a concept given by Arnett (2000) where he proposed that in post-industrial societies, there is a delay in the traditional roles and a search for stability in oneself. This distinct developmental stage spans roughly from 18-29 years of age. This period, as devised by Arnett (2000) consists of five distinct features of identity exploration, instability, self-focus, feeling-in-between and possibilities; arguing that it represents a new period in history where individuals are most deeply involved with questions of self-definition. Schwartz, Côté, and Arnett (2005) made a theoretically

important expansion of this framework by separating personal identity (the subjective sense of who one is) from social identity (the roles and group memberships through which one is recognised by others). They stated that combining these two aspects is a key developmental milestone of the emerging adult years. Additionally, emerging adulthood is a distinct phase where individuals engage in developing a narrative identity which integrates the past, present and future into a meaningful self (McAdams, 2001).

The transition from adolescence to adulthood brings a lot of significant changes for an individual. It gives them an eye-opener for what life actually feels like, what it means, making people feel every single emotional, social and personal domain of their life. This stage of life defines an individual's personality, relationships and career. Herein, the significance of life revolves around parental expectations, community and faith, financial security, independence, autonomy and the decisions relating to them are influenced by circumstances, self and many other factors (Mitra & Arnett, 2019). Self-development and interpersonal relationships reflect core features of emerging adulthood, identity exploration, self-focus and relational challenges (Louie, 2016). Young adults during this phase have stronger connections socially, high parental income and father's education level, along with greater allowance, are seen as more satisfied in their lives (Temizkan et al., 2023).

When an individual faces adversity in their childhood, it has a great impact on how an individual thinks and process situations. These adverse childhood experiences push them to take on responsibilities early within their lives and gain emotional maturity, which moulds their pace of development at a rapid pace (Johnson & Molborn, 2009). Adverse experiences during childhood can have negative influence on an individual's psychosocial well-being, affecting their self-reflection (Heo & Han, 2022). Thoits (2010) reflects that chronic stressors are particularly responsible for damaging the self as it undermines the self-concept, which is usually organised and stable. The transitional phase carries a lot of burden

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and changes, which bring in earlier responsibilities. Wherein an individual decides upon opting for the right path of tackling the major shifts on their own or becoming interdependent, resorting to social supports, impacting their career, education, relationships and family relations (Wood et al., 2017). Adversities and challenges are not only restricted to impacting not only their individual personalities but also their connections and associated support systems, leading them to focus on resilience (Livingston et al., 2025).

Supportive and healthy environments play a crucial role in the development of self during emerging adulthood period. Bronfenbrenner's ecological model (1979) provides an understanding of how the family and peer setting of an individual interact with broader cultural structures, which assists in growth of self. Luyckx, Goossens, and Soenens (2006) identified that adults who receive support from their parents are more likely to figure out who they are and be happy with themselves. This means that having people support you and having the freedom to make your choices are not opposites. Outside of family, the friends you have are really important for understanding who you are when you are becoming an adult. Qualter et al. (2015) found that having close friendships and being connected to people is really important for how you feel about yourself and how well you can deal with problems.

In collectivistic cultures, the element of harmonious society stands as the essence of it, but when we talk of this culture in the phase of Emerging Adulthood, then the role of familial self and cultural values is seen as central. In India, following the collectivistic culture, the idea of Emerging Adulthood is seen in a varied sense, where adults have to navigate through the modern aspirations and traditional influences. Many adults try to fit the traditional values into changing lifestyles, so that they may fulfil the societal expectations as well as their personal choices, creating a balance (Berry, 1997). Kakar (1978) highlighted that the Indian self is fundamentally structured around interdependence, relational embeddedness, and the internalised presence of significant others, in contrast to the autonomous individuality often regarded as normative in Western developmental theories. Roland (1988) introduced the notion of the "familial self," a form of identity formed through profound emotional entanglement with family, as emblematic of Indian psychological existence.

The current study focuses upon the adverse experiences of young adults (18-29 years), particularly those who have encountered significant changes in their childhood such as being raised by a single parent, separation of parents and loss of both parents at an early stage of life. It seeks to understand how adults have been shaped through these acknowledged adversities during the phase of

emerging adulthood. In the Indian sociocultural context, where maintaining harmony and being interdependent hold importance, how have adults been able to balance responsibilities and aspirations in the face of adversities?

By engaging with the lived experiences of these young adults, the study aims to explore how emerging adults navigate through acknowledged adversities within the Indian culture. It looks at how adverse circumstances affect their ability to handle responsibilities, deal with stress, and plan for the future. The research aims to understand how the period of Emerging Adulthood is traversed and experienced in the Indian cultural context as well as how it is shaped by adversity, ultimately attempting to provide a contextually grounded, richer and in our understanding a more adequate understanding of the emerging adults' lived reality.

Method

Research Design

This research employs a qualitative, exploratory design utilizing semi-structured interviews with individuals who have lived with adverse childhood experiences within the Indian culture. These interviews will help to uncover how individuals create meaning of their subjective experiences and developmental paths within adverse circumstances.

Paradigmatic Foundation

This research is rooted in the constructivist-interpretive paradigm, which seeks to understand how reality is socially constructed, depending upon the context. The constructivist-interpretive paradigm opts for a more personal, interactive mode of data collection based more on subjectivism, wherein the knowledge is co-constructed together through the interaction between the researcher and participants and the researcher actively interprets how participants are constructing meaning of their lived realities.

Participants

The study includes 4 young adults 2 male and 2 female, aged 18-29 years who have reportedly faced adverse life circumstances in their childhood. The focus is on individuals who belong to middle-class families and are graduates, as they are seen as drawn towards the values of Emerging Adulthood. For the research, adversity was operationalised as "distressing life events that they have personally experienced and acknowledged as emotionally challenging and disruptive for them". This was communicated to the potential participants through a flyer, which highlighted the requirements of the study along with enabling a self-selection based on the individual's perception of their adversity.

Table 1

Showing Demographics of the Participants Interviewed

Sr. no.	Name	Age	Gender	Adversity Faced
1.	GA	29 years	Male	Loss of both parents at an early age
2.	HW	24 years	Male	Loss of father at an early age
3.	AJ	22 years	Female	Separation of the parents (formal separation not through)
4.	IK	28 years	Female	Loss of both parents at an early age

Note. *For names of the participants, their initials have been used to ensure anonymity. Procedure followed for Conduct of Interviews

The semi-structured interviews were conducted in a comfortable and non-judgemental environment with adults facing adverse life problems. The interviews lasted approximately 45-60 minutes which were guided by a semi-structured interview guide, which broadly covered; a) experiences of adulthood, b) critical turning points of life for both set of participants, with reported adverse life experiences including but not limited to career transitions and challenges, relationships, friendships, familial dynamics and the like, and how do these experiences shape the person. The interviews were conducted and audio recorded with informed consent. They were assured of confidentiality and they could reach out to the researcher for any clarifications.

The study followed ethical guidelines to ensure the well-being, confidentiality and anonymity of the participants, considering the sensitivity of the adverse situations. They were assured that their identity would remain confidential and that no information would be misused. The study is being conducted only for academic research purposes. Given the sensitivity of the adverse experiences shared by participants, interviews were conducted with heightened ethical awareness and caution. The first author adopted a reflexive approach, remaining acutely sensitive to the emotional weight of the narratives. Topics that could trigger distress or discomfort were approached with care. Care was taken not to disrupt the flow of conversations. Informed consent and audio recording consent were obtained from all the participants after explaining the purpose of the study, the type of questions involved, and that their participation was voluntary. If they wished not to answer any question, they were free to do so. They were also informed of the right to withdraw from the study at any stage in case of discomfort. However, none reported any such discomfort during the interviews or at any later stage. The participants were provided with a space where they could express themselves freely about their life experiences without any judgement. The interviews were conducted in a friendly and non-judgemental environment. Participants could share their experiences at their own pace, maintaining a balance between academic inquiry

and empathetic engagement.

Analysis of Interviews

The approach of Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) was employed for this study as it is rooted in qualitative and interpretive aspects, which are utilized to understand the subjective experiences of individuals, which tells how they construct meaning of the world around them (Braun & Clarke, 2013; Braun et al., 2019). All six steps as recommended by Braun and Clarke (2006) were followed, including familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and writing up.

This constructivist and epistemological position of RTA is employed to view experiences as socially and subjectively constructed rather than fixed or universal. The initial transcription of the interviews was done manually and each transcript was read at least twice to ensure familiarity with the data. The codes were assigned to the corresponding extracts of the transcript manually. The coded extracts were grouped together into broad categories of six themes. The transcript was reviewed and understood to identify and refine themes, then each of the themes was given a name and definition. The process ensured that the themes were grounded in the participants' own lived experiences. Final themes highlight the reflexive engagement with the data.

Results

The data analysis was conducted with a focus on capturing nuanced emotional and cognitive responses of the participants, ensuring that both individual and shared experiences were considered. The researcher maintained a reflective journal throughout the process to enhance rigour and acknowledge potential biases, allowing for deeper engagement with the data. This iterative process facilitated the identification of patterns and complexities inherent in the participants' narratives, which contributed to the richness of the thematic framework.

Table 2

Thematic Analysis of Lived Experiences of Emerging Adults (18-29 years) who had Adverse Childhood Experiences

Sr no.	Themes	Subthemes	Description	Verbatims
1	Identity Formation and Self-development	<i>Search for Stability and Self Autonomy and Self Reliance</i>	The participants have highlighted how they have emerged as an individual against adverse life circumstances, wherein their identity and self, have developed along the path of growth. Along with an understanding of identity formation as non-linear and a contextually shaped Process. In the face of circumstances experienced by the participants who have shaped individuals in terms of being with limited support, an individual develops a sense of self-reliance and to make decisions of their own.	<i>“work on you. every single second, every time you get work on you” “I will be changing it. I will be moving towards what I actually love doing”. “So, that's how tables turned. And I became fearless, furious, and the way everything changed, I stopped feeling emotions”. “at that point of time, I was the one who took a stand, who just wiped my tears and I was like, okay, what happened has happened. Nothing could be changed. Now what next?”</i>
2	Negotiating Roles and Responsibilities	<i>Delayed and Evolving Roles Discipline and Responsibility Orientation</i>	Many participants have redefined the timing of their achievement of milestones shifting their sense of	<i>“I want to see.. I see myself ki I have done something in life. Now I can marry”</i>

	<i>Balancing Individualism with Collectivism</i>	individualism wherein many of them have reflected upon taking together the familial responsibilities and achieving individual stability as well. The participants have shown an emphasis over being disciplined as well as responsible, where they view these aspects of life as an exploration as well as a need to understand them as a part of their adult life. Many of the participants have highlighted how they are juggling between sticking to the Indian Cultural values along with creating a self with individualistic values, symbolising culturally embedded negotiation rather than inclination towards either of them.	<p><i>"The right time of marriage...I would not say as per the age. I would say when you think that you are independent enough to take care of your own self and the other person"</i></p> <p><i>"you should be...responsible enough just not just for yourself, but your families, those who are dependent upon you".</i></p> <p><i>"you have to be financially stable, emotionally stable, you have to be mentally mature, to handle all the to all the mishappenings".</i></p> <p><i>"aasmaan pe pahunch jao but apni roots ko mat bhulo"</i></p> <p><i>"So even if I don't get married in the traditional sense, and, you know, if I just have a partner with I can have a child...that would be enough for me"</i></p>	
3	Emotional Struggles and Psychological Impact	<i>Trust issues</i>	Due to experiences of life, participants have developed a sense of disappointment and betrayal by others which have led to a diminished sense of trust along with unwillingness towards relationships.	<p><i>"There will be people who are sweet to you on your face, but won't be on your back".</i></p> <p><i>"but iss cheez ne yahi sikhaya hai ki that you should be able to depend on yourself and not on anybody else".</i></p>
4	Resilience Through Life's Challenges	<i>Building Resilience and a Positive Outlook Social Support</i>	Participants through their life are growing and finding meaning, which helps them build resilience and a positive outlook. Their ongoing optimism showed that they were open to new ideas, which helped them keep going even when things got tough. Over time, this resilience-built self-confidence and inner strength, which helped people deal with problems better and grow psychologically. Relationships with family and friends have been a central part of participants' lives and have functioned as a source of support for them to relieve the pain and agony when faced difficulties.	<p><i>"If I have come this far, I can go much farther as well".</i></p> <p><i>"agar aisa tha ki mai bhi agar thodi zyaada agar carried away ho jaati then things...would have definitely fallen apart. So somebody had to be the pillar... of the family".</i></p> <p><i>"Even if I talk about my friends, they have been in....every part of my life from, you know, um....when I needed them, when I lost my mother, they were there with me. When I needed a job, they were there with me".</i></p> <p><i>"immediate supportive were my friends...who were there the entire night when my father was in uh.. was a ventilator in the hospital. So I didn't have to look anywhere elsewhere my friends were there"</i></p>
5	Societal Pressures and Restraints	<i>Cultural and Societal constraints</i>	Within the Indian cultural context, society plays a vital role in determining an individual's interests and aspirations, where the participants have described feelings of restriction by societal expectations of adherence to the norms.	<p><i>"baaki log kya kahenge aap India mein reh rahe ho aap....society ke baare mein pehle sochne lag jaate ho ki kya kahenge..."</i></p> <p><i>"If I take such step, what will people say?.. Who will take care of me? If I would have my parents behind my back, I would have just</i></p>

6 Future Orientation
and Life Approach

*Learning and Growth
Mindset
Clear and Practical
Thinking*

For many participants, their life experiences have become a source of lessons for their personal growth. Difficulties are not perceived as a setback here, whereas it enhances the sense of self-understanding and building of inner strength. Here, the participants have reflected the emotional maturity and development of an approach to life which is realistic and are with clarity of how to reach out to new experiences in their lives. For many, adversity had stripped them of their idealism and replaced it with a clearer assessment of their situation. This practical thinking gives them the ability to move forward with more direction and purpose rather than as a loss.

left everything and gone to my parents. Now, where would I go?''.
''The only thing is you should not take a wrong decision. matlab... agar... tum koi risk le rahe ho toh it should be a calculative one. If you are going for something different that you are uh..from what you are currently doing, you should have proper guidance where you are jumping into''.
''so i know i can take care of myself i know what is right what is wrong for me''.
''you should have the clarity what do you want to do because I have seen people who are going to their higher studies in early thirties as well after quitting job. So, because they didn't have the clarity earlier. So...the sooner the better, what I want to say''.

Discussion

The present study illuminates the lived experiences of young adults (18-29 years) who have faced adversities and how the experience has been shaped throughout their lives due to those circumstances within the Indian Context. Six themes have been evident across the semi-structured interviews using the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). These themes highlight that life challenges and adversities play a key role in shaping an individual's sense of self.

The first theme of Identity formation and Self-development highlights that the participants are engaged in an ongoing process of self-exploration, where they are striving to achieve stability, achievement and growth. Marcia (1966) devised identity through exploration and commitment, which provided a varied path through which the self can be constructed during a transitional phase of life. The participants have reflected through their narratives that they are still trying to explore themselves through relationships and career. Rather identity formation being a gradual and exploratory process, due to hardships and adversities, their formation of identity was a result of urgency, requirement and a necessity but still they are juggling between their own aspirations where they wish to create a stable career and look for a settled future with their own families. A participant reported that he is in a stable job but wishes to make an upside-down change in his life within a span of 2-3 years as he was there just for the money as he wanted to stabilize himself a little after the loss of his parents, which shows that adversity has pushed him into something he never wanted and at current he looks for a new life which he desires. This shows that emerging adults are still taking their chances in life despite stability and they are searching for something that they wish to achieve, they are not putting a full stop as they have reached a milestone; they still reflect a life of opportunities. They are instead focused on possibilities and future

goals, which fits with the idea of compulsory individualisation, where people have to actively shape their own lives through long-term self-improvement plans and thinking about "who they are," balancing their own choices with the limits of the system (Cote, 2002). The sub-theme of autonomy and self-reliance reflects their development as not a choice but a necessity by adverse circumstances, by one of the participants stating, "*iss cheez ne yahi sikhaya hai ki you should be able to depend on yourself and not on anybody else*". The experiences of living with a single parent (adversity) have nurtured this thought of not relying upon someone and making oneself a more independent person. Emerging adults have an impact on their environment since childhood and those experiences of adversities shape their orientation towards life of gaining a more self-sustained self. This perspective aligns with individuals experiencing adverse childhood events exhibiting self-reliance as a coping mechanism (Askaree et al., 2025).

During this exploration of identity, one develops different roles and responsibilities, discovers new aspects within their lives to shape their understanding of self. The second theme of negotiating roles and responsibilities highlights the balancing of the roles and responsibilities and a negotiation between the cultural-familial expectations, along with a desire for autonomy. Within the Indian culture, it is considered important to reach certain milestones and take on the traditional roles according to the time which is set by society. But the emerging adults are trying to balance their collectivistic and individualistic orientations of life, wherein they stay connected to the societal values and beliefs but are also working on achieving their individual goals to fulfil their aspirations. This resonates with the concept of autonomous relational self by Kagitcibasi (1996) where it has been described that individuals strive to maintain emotional interdependence while achieving personal autonomy. As one participant stated, "*aasmaan pe pahunch*

jao but apni roots ko mat bhulo”, this shows that their culture and societal values act as a base in their process of developing their own self. Here, they want to achieve excellence but also keep their cultural understandings intact. During the course of narrative, the participant mentioned spirituality and along with this aspect of spirituality, he also reflects upon a close bond with his mother, which connects him to his traditional roles and collectivistic values. At the same time, he highlights his inclination towards a riskier and more exploratory side, where he is trying to focus on change and personal growth. This shows that emerging adulthood is a time of more exploration and risk-taking as people gain more independence and try out different life options, such as beliefs, relationships, and personal choices (Mitra & Arnett, 2019). The participant's transition between spirituality and risk-taking exemplifies the dynamic interaction of stability and exploration, wherein identity is actively formed through both established connections and exploratory experiences. As a result, it reflects that within the Indian context, an emerging adult constantly moves between individualistic and collectivistic orientations, to attain greater changes, and give space to passions that align with the familial expectations. This highlights that in every culture, the concept of Emerging Adulthood takes a different form (Arnett, 2007) reflecting the importance of culturally situated understanding.

With the balancing of the two orientations of individualism and collectivism, the adult navigates through the delaying of their roles and responsibilities, where many participants have redefined the timing of their achievement of milestones, wherein many of them have reflected upon the prioritisation of a stability of self over the traditional timing of marriage. A participant highlighted that, *“The right time of marriage...I would not say as per the age. I would say when you think that you are independent enough to take care of your own self and the other person”*. Many participants have redefined the timing of their achievement of milestones, shifting their sense of individualism, wherein many of them have reflected upon taking together the familial responsibilities and achieving individual stability as well. This participant had to take on an early responsibility of getting married even when she wasn't ready due to the loss of both parents in early life, and when we talk of marriage in Indian culture, it is not merely a union between two individuals, but it entails shared familial commitments and increased responsibilities. This resonates with the finding by Narayan (2024), reflecting that numerous Indian emerging adults still continue to aim for traditional milestones such as marriage and stable employment while navigating through the changing social contexts as well. This contrasts with the western contexts, where emerging adults are engaging in identity exploration and different living arrangements such as live-in, cohabitation and delayed commitments, reflecting greater autonomy. However, negative life events can make this exploration harder, forcing people, especially women in India, to take on adult roles earlier than is normal for their development, which limits their chances to learn about themselves. This also captures that in the face of adverse circumstances, the individual gains an understanding of first becoming settled in life financially, getting more inclined towards an independent self and then only step into the stairs towards marriage. In India, this delay is often negotiated within collectivistic expectations, where family pressures for early stability coexist with more chances for longer education and career exploration. This creates a conflict between traditional timelines and changing goals.

The findings highlight that participants encountered considerable emotional challenges faced during their childhood, underscoring the psychological burden of this transitional period (Theme three). The ongoing process of forming an identity and the instability of life seem to be linked to feelings of stress, confusion, and emotional turmoil within the adversities and struggles. *“The most significant thing that has happened would be my parents' separation, I would say. So, they're not quite fully reversed yet...But hann..I think that the separation has really shaped me who I am as a person”*, (formal separation not through) as stated by a participant. The adverse circumstances within an individual's life plays a pivotal role in shaping their self. The individuals become more responsible, self-reliant, resilient and it also pushes an individual to value their relations and family within their life. This aligns with the existing literature that states that the adverse childhood experiences have a significant impact on psycho-emotional well-being and overall quality of life (Gkiouzeli et al., 2026). The adversities of an individual's life not only shape them more positively but also can affect their mental health and can even elicit *trust issues*. Across the interviews, it was observed that the adversities faced by the individuals have transformed their conception of trust and belief in others, for instance, as stated by a participant, *“There will be people who are sweet to you on your face, but won't be on your back”*. This shows that the emerging adults face an unstable sense of putting faith in others due to past experiences. Additionally, it was seen that although participants had a profound yearning for connection and emotional intimacy, they concurrently employed self-protective distancing mechanisms by engaging in casual relationships or avoiding the relationship aspect of their lives at present. Despite emotional struggles, young adults face an inability to form relationships due to adverse childhood experiences but the individuals withstand those challenges by constantly working on their trust issues over a period of time. This pattern of protective engagement contrasts with the evidence suggesting that individuals who have experienced fewer adversities and favourable life conditions become more open to cooperating with others (Mell et al., 2021).

Moving through the experiences of forming a sense of self through faced hardships and struggles, the individuals tend to develop stress management strategies and try to find ways through which they can cope with their challenges. Theme four of Resilience through life's challenges captures that the resilience built within the participants is due to experiences of life and not as an innate trait. One of the participants stated that, *“agar aisa tha ki mai bhi agar thodi zyaada agar carried away ho jaati then things...would have definitely fallen apart. So, somebody had to be the pillar... of the family”*. The major life challenges have persisted through their childhood and the nature of every adversity was different for each individual, such as loss of parents at an early age, ongoing separation of parents and living with a single parent. These adverse situations push the emerging adults to stand through thick and thin, becoming resilient. This resonates with the finding that resilience is considered a dynamic system of capacity that adapts successfully to disturbances that threaten the system's function and development (Masten, 2001). The participants have utilized coping mechanisms such as engaging in workout, spirituality, watching shows, movies, opting for a business that keeps them busy as shared by one of the participant that they have built upon a business for her that keeps her busy and she takes it as a way to distract herself from the stressful

situations that she encounters which has eventually assisted her in dealing with the challenges and becoming resilient. This highlights that the coping strategies are unique for everyone and are found to be developed more consistently with post-traumatic growth (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004). The situation for a young adult becomes better through resilience, but every participant's scars from the adverse circumstances still have a negative impact on their psyche, making sense of their experiences to date. Becoming resilient helps an individual to become internally strong and every person requires some sense of external support to thrive through their challenges. This external support comes through an individual's support systems, which are considered to be the pillar of an individual's developmental phase of life, assisting them to navigate through the path in an easier manner. Families and friends are the strengths of an individual during adversities; they help in overcoming those disruptions by becoming one's right hand. In India, the emphasis of an adult revolves around their family, as there is more of a harmonious outlook towards life, keeping a family-centric orientation. In the face of adversities, individuals feel a sense of connection towards their family and view them as a priority. This resonates with the finding of Chadda and Deb (2013) which emphasises that Indian families are capable of meeting the physical, spiritual, and emotional needs of their members.

Within the Indian socio-cultural context, individuals experience a self that is bounded by society. The growth of an adult accounts for relational self, which forms them through the culture and harmonious orientation as a central point of development within the Indian Context. The theme five shows that participants' sense of self is greatly affected by societal pressures and structural constraints. Expectations regarding career success, financial stability, and compliance with familial roles surfaced as significant influences, frequently limiting personal agency and exacerbating internal conflict. A participant described this feeling of restraint as, "*baaki log kya kahenge aap India mein reh rahe ho aap...society ke baare mein pehle sochne lag jaate ho ki kya kahenge...*" This also shows a sense of self-doubt developed within their minds due to societal judgement. This results in the formation of a fragmented self, which involves an ongoing process of negotiating and compromising oneself for society. Individuals experience the tug-of-war between the need for autonomy and self-realization, on the one side, and the need to comply and maintain social harmony, on the other. Fragmentation does not happen through clear separation but through the constant struggle between these opposing aspects, where neither can achieve satisfaction. It appears that any decision made regarding a career choice, relationship, way of life, and even values become a matter of such struggle, since it forces the person to choose between fulfilling personal desires and following the social norm. The internalized form of social monitoring faced by the participants has a resemblance to the findings of Pandey and Singh (2024) who point out that in the Indian scenario, stigmatization is a socio-cultural phenomenon where the individual begins to expect and avoid being judged by society, which ultimately leads to the loss of self-respect and ability to express oneself independently of social norms. Thus, the process of living is transformed into an eternal battle, which leaves one's sense of self in constant uncertainty between personal and social identity. The societal pressures faced by participants mirror broader structural and cultural dynamics in the Indian context, where emerging adulthood is marked by instability, identity exploration, and relational expectations (Mitra & Arnett, 2025).

Lastly, theme six reflects that despite the adversities, disruptions and pressures described by the participants, they are oriented towards a future, which resonates with Arnett's (2000) emerging adulthood feature of possibilities. One of the participants reported that, "*The only thing is you should not take a wrong decision. matlab... agar... tum koi risk le rahe ho toh it should be a calculative one. If you are going for something different that you are uh..from what you are currently doing, you should have proper guidance where you are jumping into*". This participant had regrets about not making decisions in a timely and due to the loss of his parents, he could not get proper guidance from anyone regarding his career choices. This had led him to think about the future in a positive sense and understand that every step in life has to be taken strategically. Due to adversities, emerging adults learn to develop a more optimistic perspective towards life. The difficult circumstances make them better rather than causing damage. By this time, they also start developing a more *pragmatic thinking* towards life. Across the interviews, it was observed that the participants can make decisions of their own and understand the sense of what is right and wrong. Adults during the phase of emerging adulthood become more practical, which helps them throughout their growth towards becoming adults. This aligns with a finding that reports there is an inclination to positivity and curiosity of decision making and risks, reflecting a more adaptive and growth-focused perspective in life, which enhances practical competence in young adults (Oshri et al., 2018). Instead of just causing harm, adversity seems to help people grow in a way that helps them adapt. This means that people learn to deal with problems in a way that is positive, clear, and focused on their future goals.

Limitations and Suggestions

Despite the study's useful contributions, it highlights some limitations. The qualitative design and the relatively small, context-specific sample restrict the applicability of findings to dissimilar sociocultural contexts. The dependence on self-reported accounts may result in recall bias and subjective reinterpretations of previous adversities. Furthermore, the application of Reflexive Thematic Analysis entails interpretative subjectivity, which, while beneficial, may be affected by the researcher's bias. Additionally, the study may be influenced by the paradox of disclosure, where participants may simultaneously feel compelled to share their experiences while also concealing or filtering sensitive information due to discomfort, social desirability, or fear of judgement, potentially constraining the depth and authenticity of narratives. Moreover, the study fails to adequately consider variations in gender, socioeconomic status, or regional diversity, which could provide a more nuanced understanding of emerging adulthood in India.

Implications of the Study

The findings have important implications in research, policy, and psychological practice. Interventions for emerging adults must go beyond deficit-based methodologies and acknowledge resilience as a dynamic and contextually influenced process. Mental health professionals should use culturally sensitive frameworks that take into account family interdependence, social pressures, and early role changes. It also provides an understanding of what can be done in terms of counselling services and what support can be provided through governmental as well as non-governmental organisations. Schools and policymakers should make environments that are

helpful for both learning and exploring, especially for people who are going through hard times early on. Strengthening support systems, especially family and community networks, can help young adults cope better and grow in other ways.

Conclusion

The current research emphasises that emerging adulthood in the Indian context is not solely a time of exploration and instability, as suggested by Arnett (2000) but a phase that is influenced by adversity and sociocultural expectations. The findings indicate that adversities concurrently disrupt, reshape and alter developmental phases, promoting premature responsibility, identity reconfiguration, and resilience. Although participants faced emotional challenges and societal limitations, they exhibited growth-oriented future outlooks and pragmatic decision-making, rooted in their specific contexts. In India, emerging adulthood is a dynamic interplay between vulnerability and strength, where hardship often leads to both psychological growth and practical skills.

Future research could benefit from broader and more diverse samples to reflect regional and cultural differences. Secondly, it can also focus on a uniform set of adversities to address a greater understanding of the experiences. Longitudinal studies would be valuable in tracking individuals, which could reveal patterns: how hardship shifts, how strength grows, what shapes growth along the way. Additionally, exploration of gendered experiences and changing technologies would enrich the understanding of emerging adulthood.

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Received March 12, 2026

Revision received April 8, 2026

Accepted April 10, 2026